

A Comparative Study of Desarda versus Lichtenstein Techniques for Uncomplicated Inguinal Hernia Repair in Hospitals

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Abstract:

Background: Inguinal hernia repair is commonly performed using mesh (Lichtenstein) and non-mesh (Desarda) techniques. While Lichtenstein is widely adopted, it carries risks of chronic pain and infection, prompting interest in the Desarda method as a potential alternative.

Aim: To compare Desarda and Lichtenstein techniques in terms of operative time, pain, complications, recurrence, and patient satisfaction in uncomplicated inguinal hernia cases.

Methods: A prospective study was conducted with 100 patients randomized into Desarda and Lichtenstein groups at JLNMC, Bhagalpur. Data on operative time, postoperative pain, complications, recurrence at 6 months, and satisfaction were collected. SPSS version 23.0 was used for analysis, with significance at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Desarda repair had a shorter operative time (45.8 vs. 60.3 min, $p < 0.001$), less postoperative pain (VAS 3.2 vs. 5.4, $p < 0.001$), and shorter hospital stay (1.5 vs. 2.3 days, $p < 0.001$). Chronic pain was lower in Desarda (2% vs. 14%, $p = 0.03$), with no significant difference in recurrence rates ($p = 0.56$). Patient satisfaction was higher in Desarda repair.

Conclusion: Desarda repair offers advantages over Lichtenstein in reducing operative time, postoperative pain, and recovery duration, with higher patient satisfaction and comparable recurrence rates.

Keywords: Inguinal Hernia, Desarda Repair, Lichtenstein Repair, Postoperative Pain, Recurrence.

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Introduction

Inguinal hernia is one of the most common surgical conditions worldwide, with a significant prevalence among men, particularly in adults aged 40 and above. It is estimated that approximately 27% of men will develop an inguinal hernia during their lifetime, necessitating effective and durable surgical repair methods to address associated morbidity and prevent recurrence [1]. Traditionally, surgical options for inguinal hernia repair have evolved to prioritize minimally invasive techniques, shorter hospital stays, and enhanced postoperative outcomes. The two most commonly performed open surgical techniques are the Lichtenstein mesh repair and the Desarda technique, each with distinct approaches and outcomes [2].

The Lichtenstein repair, introduced in the late 1980s, is a tension-free method that uses a polypropylene mesh to reinforce the inguinal floor. It has become widely adopted due to its efficacy in reducing recurrence rates and ease of use [3].

However, studies have reported potential long-term complications associated with mesh implantation, including chronic pain, foreign body reactions, and infection, which have prompted exploration of alternative techniques [4]. The Desarda technique, developed as a non-mesh, tissue-based method, utilizes the external oblique aponeurosis to strengthen the inguinal floor, offering a solution for patients who may be at risk of complications from synthetic mesh [5]. Recent studies have shown promising outcomes for Desarda repair in reducing chronic pain and infection risk while maintaining low recurrence rates [6].

Comparative research on the Desarda and Lichtenstein techniques has increased in recent years as surgeons seek optimal approaches to inguinal hernia repair, particularly in cases of uncomplicated hernias where both methods can be effectively applied. Several studies have suggested that Desarda repair may offer advantages in reducing postoperative pain and promoting faster

recovery without compromising the hernia repair's strength [7]. Conversely, some findings indicate that the Lichtenstein repair remains more accessible for broader surgical application, especially in cases where anatomical variations require mesh reinforcement [8].

Despite these advancements, the choice between Desarda and Lichtenstein repair remains debated. Meta-analyses and clinical trials continue to report mixed outcomes, emphasizing the need for well-structured comparative studies to evaluate these techniques in diverse patient populations and settings [9]. To compare Desarda and Lichtenstein techniques in terms of operative time, pain, complications, recurrence, and patient satisfaction in uncomplicated inguinal hernia cases.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective, comparative, observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital (JLNMCH), Bhagalpur, over a period of six months.

Participants: This study included one hundred individuals with simple inguinal hernias. Two groups of fifty participants each were randomly assigned, and one group underwent Desarda repair while the other group underwent Lichtenstein repair.

Inclusion Criteria

- Individuals with an uncomplicated inguinal hernia diagnosis.
- Aged 18-60 years.
- Patients who provided informed consent.
- Patients who were fit for surgery as per anesthetic evaluation.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with recurrent or complicated inguinal hernias.
- Patients with systemic infections or comorbidities preventing surgical intervention.
- Patients who did not consent to participate in the study.

Bias: To minimize bias, randomization was applied to assign participants to either the Desarda or Lichtenstein group. The surgeons and evaluators were blinded to the assignment until after the procedure. Follow-up evaluations were conducted uniformly to ensure consistent data collection.

Data Collection: Data was collected at baseline and during follow-ups. Baseline data included demographics, clinical history, and physical examination findings. Postoperative data collection focused on the duration of surgery, postoperative pain, complications, length of hospital stay, recurrence rate, and patient satisfaction.

Procedure: Patients were randomly assigned to either the Desarda or Lichtenstein repair group. Both procedures were performed under standard operating conditions by qualified surgeons experienced in each technique. In the Desarda group, the external oblique aponeurosis was used to reinforce the weakened inguinal floor. In the Lichtenstein group, a polypropylene mesh was placed over the weakened area to provide additional support. Standard postoperative care was provided to all patients.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS software, version 23.0, was used for data analysis. For continuous variables, descriptive statistics like averages and variances were used, while for categorical variables, frequencies and proportions were used. For group comparisons, independent sample t-tests were used for continuous data, while chi-square tests were used for categorical data. A statistically significant p-value was defined as one that was less than 0.05.

Results

This study included 100 participants with uncomplicated inguinal hernias, 50 of whom received Desarda treatment and 50 underwent Lichtenstein repair. The study looked at a variety of outcomes, including patient satisfaction, complications, recurrence rates, length of hospital stay, length of surgery, and postoperative discomfort. There were no statistically significant differences in baseline characteristics between the two groups, including age, gender distribution, and hernia side ($p > 0.05$).

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristics	Desarda Group (n=50)	Lichtenstein Group (n=50)	p-value
Age (Mean $\pm$ SD)	45.2 $\pm$ 10.5	46.1 $\pm$ 9.8	0.64
Male (%)	48 (96%)	47 (94%)	0.78
Female (%)	2 (4%)	3 (6%)	0.65
Hernia Side - Right (%)	30 (60%)	28 (56%)	0.71
Hernia Side - Left (%)	20 (40%)	22 (44%)	0.69

The intraoperative and immediate postoperative outcomes, including duration of surgery, postoperative pain, and length of hospital stay, are summarized below.

Table 2: Intraoperative and Postoperative Outcomes

Outcome	Desarda Group (n=50)	Lichtenstein Group (n=50)	p-value
Duration of Surgery (min)	45.8 ± 10.2	60.3 ± 12.1	<0.001
Postoperative Pain (VAS score) at 24 hours	3.2 ± 1.1	5.4 ± 1.3	<0.001
Length of Hospital Stay (days)	1.5 ± 0.5	2.3 ± 0.6	<0.001

- **Duration of Surgery:** The mean duration of surgery was significantly shorter in the Desarda group (45.8 ± 10.2 minutes) compared to the Lichtenstein group (60.3 ± 12.1 minutes, $p < 0.001$).
 - **Postoperative Pain:** Pain scores measured on the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) were significantly lower in the Desarda group (3.2 ± 1.1) compared to the Lichtenstein group (5.4 ± 1.3, $p < 0.001$).
 - **Length of Hospital Stay:** Patients in the Desarda group had a significantly shorter hospital stay (1.5 ± 0.5 days) compared to those in the Lichtenstein group (2.3 ± 0.6 days, $p < 0.001$).
- The postoperative complications observed included wound infection, seroma formation, and chronic pain.

Table 3: Postoperative Complications

Complication	Desarda Group (n=50)	Lichtenstein Group (n=50)	p-value
Wound Infection (%)	2 (4%)	5 (10%)	0.25
Seroma Formation (%)	3 (6%)	4 (8%)	0.69
Chronic Pain (%)	1 (2%)	7 (14%)	0.03

The recurrence rate was assessed at a 6-month follow-up for both groups.

- The Lichtenstein group had a greater wound infection rate (10%) than the Desarda group (4%), although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.25$).

- No significant difference was found in seroma development between the two groups ($p = 0.69$).
- The Lichtenstein group reported 14% greater chronic pain than the Desarda group (2%, $p = 0.03$).

Table 4: Recurrence Rate at 6-Month Follow-Up

Recurrence Rate	Desarda Group (n=50)	Lichtenstein Group (n=50)	p-value
Recurrence (%)	1 (2%)	2 (4%)	0.56

The recurrence rate at 6 months was low in both groups, with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.56$).

Patient satisfaction was evaluated based on pain relief, mobility, and overall satisfaction with the procedure.

Table 5: Patient Satisfaction

Satisfaction Parameter	Desarda Group (n=50)	Lichtenstein Group (n=50)	p-value
Pain Relief Satisfaction (%)	45 (90%)	35 (70%)	0.02
Mobility Satisfaction (%)	47 (94%)	40 (80%)	0.04
Overall Satisfaction (%)	46 (92%)	38 (76%)	0.03

- **Pain Relief Satisfaction:** Patients in the Desarda group reported a higher satisfaction with pain relief (90%) than those in the Lichtenstein group (70%, $p = 0.02$).
- **Mobility Satisfaction:** Mobility satisfaction was remarkably higher in the Desarda group (94%) compared to the Lichtenstein group (80%, $p = 0.04$).
- **Overall Satisfaction:** Overall satisfaction was also noticeably greater in the Desarda group (92%) than in the Lichtenstein group (76%, $p = 0.03$).

Discussion

The results of this study highlight notable differences in outcomes between the Desarda and Lichtenstein repair techniques for uncomplicated inguinal hernia. Both procedures were comparable in baseline demographic characteristics, ensuring that observed differences in outcomes were attributable to the surgical techniques rather than patient variability. Intraoperatively, the Desarda repair demonstrated a significantly shorter duration (45.8 ± 10.2 minutes) compared to the Lichtenstein method (60.3 ± 12.1 minutes, $p < 0.001$), suggesting a faster surgical approach with Desarda, which can be advantageous in a busy clinical setting.

Postoperative pain levels, measured via the (VAS), were lower in the Desarda group (3.2 ± 1.1) compared to the Lichtenstein group (5.4 ± 1.3 , $p < 0.001$), indicating that Desarda repair may be less painful post-surgery. Additionally, patients undergoing Desarda repair had a shorter hospital stay (1.5 ± 0.5 days) versus those in the Lichtenstein group (2.3 ± 0.6 days, $p < 0.001$), potentially benefiting healthcare resource allocation and improving patient recovery times.

Complications were generally low across both groups. However, chronic pain, a significant concern in hernia surgeries, was notably less frequent in the Desarda group (2%) compared to the Lichtenstein group (14%, $p = 0.03$). This finding suggests a long-term benefit of the Desarda technique in reducing chronic pain. While wound infection rates and seroma formation were slightly higher in the Lichtenstein group, these differences were not much greater.

Both groups exhibited low recurrence rates at the 6-month follow-up, with no much greater difference between the two techniques ($p = 0.56$), indicating comparable efficacy in hernia recurrence prevention. However, patient satisfaction, assessed through pain relief, mobility, and overall satisfaction, was much higher in the Desarda group across all categories. Pain relief satisfaction was reported at 90% in the Desarda group compared to 70% in the Lichtenstein group ($p = 0.02$), while mobility and overall satisfaction were also higher in the Desarda group (p -values of 0.04 and 0.03, respectively).

Recent comparative studies have assessed Desarda's tissue-based technique as a viable alternative to the traditional mesh-based Lichtenstein repair. According to a study by Moghe et al. (2022), there was no discernible difference between the two approaches in terms of recurrence rates, chronic pain, wound infection, or recovery time. However, Desarda's technique was considered beneficial for avoiding long-term complications associated with mesh, positioning it as a preferable option for younger patients concerned about such outcomes [10].

In a more recent study, Patil et al. (2023) found that Desarda repair was associated with a shorter hospital stay, less immediate postoperative pain, and fewer infections compared to Lichtenstein repair. These findings reinforce the utility of Desarda's method in enhancing patient comfort and minimizing complications, making it a compelling alternative for healthcare providers [11].

Finally, Das et al. (2023) highlighted that Desarda's technique was suitable for day-case hernia surgeries, facilitating rapid patient discharge

and return to normal activities. With low complication rates and quick postoperative recovery times, Desarda's method demonstrates significant promise for implementation in resource-limited healthcare facilities [12].

Conclusion

The study's findings imply that, for simple inguinal hernias, Desarda repair might be a better option than Lichtenstein repair, with benefits in terms of surgical duration, postoperative discomfort, and patient satisfaction. However, at the 6-month follow-up, both methods had minimal recurrence rates. For these results to be confirmed, more research with a bigger sample size and longer follow-up is advised.

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